
Role of Academic Libraries in Promoting Open Access and Enhancing Research Visibility in Nigerian Universities

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates how academic libraries in Nigerian universities promote open access initiatives and enhance research visibility, focusing on promotion, utilization, and strategic approaches. A descriptive-survey design was adopted, targeting 255 academic staff across selected universities in Oyo State, Nigeria. Data were collected via a structured questionnaire covering open access promotion, utilization and research visibility. Data were analysed using descriptive statistics, Pearson correlation, and multiple regression with SPSS. Results indicate that utilization of open access platforms positively and significantly influences research visibility ($\beta = 0.428, p < 0.001$). Open access promotion alone did not significantly affect visibility ($\beta = 0.035, p > 0.05$). Combined, Open access variables explained 18% of the variance in research visibility ($R^2 = 0.186, p < 0.001$). The study concludes that the effectiveness of open access initiatives in enhancing research visibility depends largely on the extent of active utilization by academic staff rather than on promotional efforts alone. It is therefore recommended that academic libraries prioritize user-centered strategies, including targeted training, strengthened institutional policies, and enhanced repository management, to encourage active engagement with open access platforms and maximize research visibility.

KEYWORDS: Academic libraries, Open access, Research visibility, Institutional repositories

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1.1 BACKGROUND TO THE STUDY

The rapid evolution of scholarly communication in the digital age has significantly altered how research outputs are produced, disseminated, and accessed. Traditionally, access to scholarly publications was restricted through subscription-based models, limiting the visibility and impact of research, particularly in developing countries such as Nigeria. The emergence of open access has addressed these limitations by enabling free and unrestricted access to scholarly works, thereby enhancing knowledge sharing and global academic collaboration. Open access has become a critical component of modern research ecosystems, as it improves the accessibility, usage, and citation of scholarly outputs (Jain, 2012)

In Nigeria, the challenge of limited access to scholarly resources has historically hindered research productivity and visibility. Many universities face financial constraints that restrict their ability to subscribe to high-cost academic journals, resulting in reduced access to current research findings. Consequently, Nigerian scholars often experience low global visibility and limited citation impact. This situation underscores the need for alternative dissemination models such as open access, which provide cost-effective means of sharing research outputs widely. Ezema (2011) emphasizes that improving access to Nigerian research through open access platforms is essential for increasing its global visibility and scholarly impact.

Academic libraries have emerged as key drivers of open access initiatives within universities. Traditionally responsible for the acquisition, organization, and dissemination of information resources, academic libraries are now actively involved in managing digital repositories, supporting open access publishing, and promoting scholarly communication. Institutional repositories (IRs), which are typically managed by university libraries, serve as digital archives that preserve and disseminate research outputs such as theses, dissertations, and journal articles. These repositories play a significant role in enhancing the visibility and accessibility of research produced within Nigerian universities (Adeyemo & Jamogha, 2021).

Furthermore, academic libraries engage in advocacy and capacity-building efforts aimed at increasing awareness and adoption of open access among researchers. Librarians provide training on self-archiving, copyright management, and the use of digital platforms for research dissemination. Such initiatives are essential for improving researchers' ability to share their work effectively and maximize its impact. Studies have shown that research outputs deposited in open access repositories are more easily discoverable through search engines and tend to receive higher citation rates, thereby enhancing research visibility (Orsu, 2019). Despite these advancements, the promotion of open access in Nigerian universities faces several challenges. These include inadequate funding, poor information and communication technology (ICT) infrastructure, low awareness among academic staff, and the absence of comprehensive institutional policies to support open access initiatives. Ezema and Okafor (2015) note that these challenges limit the effectiveness of institutional repositories and hinder the full realization of open access benefits in Nigerian academic institutions. More recent studies confirm that these issues persist, affecting the ability of academic libraries to enhance research visibility effectively (Ezema & Eze, 2024). Given the increasing importance of global research visibility and the growing adoption of open access worldwide, it is imperative to examine the role of academic libraries in promoting open access within Nigerian universities. Understanding how libraries contribute to the dissemination and visibility of research outputs, as well as the challenges they face, is essential for developing strategies that will strengthen open access initiatives and improve the global impact of Nigerian scholarship.

1.2 LITERATURE REVIEW

The transformation of scholarly communication through open access has significantly repositioned academic libraries as key actors in enhancing research visibility. Open access eliminates financial and legal barriers to scholarly information, thereby increasing the accessibility, usage, and citation of research outputs. In developing countries such as Nigeria, where access to subscription-based resources is constrained, academic libraries play a pivotal role in facilitating open access adoption and improving the global visibility of local research. One of the primary mechanisms through which academic libraries promote open access is the development and management of institutional repositories (IRs). Institutional repositories serve as digital platforms for preserving and disseminating scholarly outputs, including journal articles, theses, and conference papers. Ezema (2011) argues that IRs significantly enhance the global visibility of Nigerian research by ensuring wider dissemination and accessibility of scholarly works. Similarly, Adeyemo and Jamogha (2021) highlight that effective repository management contributes to improved university web rankings and international recognition. Beyond repository development, academic libraries engage in advocacy and awareness creation to encourage researchers to adopt open access publishing. Baro and Eze (2017) report that although awareness of open access among Nigerian librarians is relatively high, sustained advocacy is required to translate awareness into active participation. This suggests that libraries must move beyond awareness campaigns to implementing structured support systems that facilitate researchers' engagement with open access platforms.

Training and capacity building constitute another critical role of academic libraries. Librarians provide guidance on self-archiving, copyright management, and the selection of reputable open access journals. Chukwueke (2020) notes that such training initiatives improve researchers' competence in disseminating their work through open access channels, thereby enhancing visibility and citation impact. These findings align with broader studies that link digital literacy support from libraries to improved research dissemination outcomes. Empirical evidence also indicates a strong relationship between open access adoption and research visibility. Onyebinama and Ngozi (2024) demonstrate that open access publishing leads to increased citation rates and broader dissemination of scholarly outputs in Nigerian universities). Orsu (2019) similarly observes that publications deposited in open access repositories are more easily indexed by search engines such as Google Scholar, thereby improving discoverability and academic impact. These findings reinforce the argument that open access serves as a critical driver of research visibility in the digital age.

Despite these contributions, several structural and institutional challenges limit the effectiveness of academic libraries in promoting open access in Nigeria. Ezema and Okafor (2015) identify inadequate funding, poor technological infrastructure, and lack of institutional policies as major barriers to the development and sustainability of institutional repositories. More recent evidence by Ezema and Eze (2024) confirms that these challenges persist, particularly in terms of technical capacity and policy implementation, thereby constraining the impact of open access initiatives. Furthermore, the gap between awareness and utilization of open access resources remains a critical issue. Horsfall et al. (2025) report that while many librarians and researchers are aware of open access initiatives, actual usage is hindered by insufficient training and limited institutional support. This highlights the need for more integrated strategies that combine advocacy, infrastructure development, and policy enforcement. Overall, the literature underscores that academic libraries in Nigerian universities are central to the promotion of open access and the enhancement of research visibility. Their roles span repository development, advocacy, training, and technical support. However, the effectiveness of these roles is moderated by persistent infrastructural, financial, and policy-related challenges. Addressing

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these constraints is essential for maximizing the potential of open access in improving the global visibility and impact of Nigerian research.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

Although Open Access publishing has the potential to significantly improve the visibility and impact of research outputs, Nigerian universities continue to experience low global research visibility. This is evident in poor representation in global rankings and limited citation impact of locally produced research. While institutional repositories and other Open Access initiatives have been established in many Nigerian universities, their utilization remains suboptimal. Studies reveal that although awareness of repositories exists, consistent usage and engagement by researchers are still moderate. Moreover, the role of academic libraries in promoting Open Access has not been fully maximized due to challenges such as inadequate training, lack of technical support, and weak institutional policies. Consequently, there is a need to critically examine how academic libraries contribute to Open Access promotion and how this influences the visibility of Nigerian research outputs.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The research objectives are to:

1. examine the extent of open access promotion by academic libraries in universities in Oyo State, Nigeria.
2. assess the level of research visibility among academic staff in universities in Oyo State, Nigeria.
3. determine the level of awareness and utilization of open access platforms among academic staff.
4. examine the relationship between open access promotion and research visibility.
5. determine the relationship between utilization of open access platforms and research visibility.
6. evaluate the joint effect of open access promotion and utilization on research visibility.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

1. What is the extent of open access promotion by academic libraries in universities in Oyo State, Nigeria?
2. What is the level of research visibility among academic staff in universities in Oyo State, Nigeria?
3. What is the level of awareness and utilization of open access platforms among academic staff?

RESEARCH HYPOTHESES

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between open access promotion by academic libraries and research visibility in universities in Oyo State, Nigeria.

H₀₂: There is no significant relationship between the utilization of open access platforms by academic staff and research visibility in universities in Oyo State, Nigeria.

H₀₃: Open access promotion and utilization do not jointly have a significant influence on research visibility among academic staff in universities in Oyo State, Nigeria.

STATEMENT OF PROBLEM

Despite the global shift toward open access publishing as a means of enhancing the visibility and impact of scholarly research, Nigerian universities continue to experience low global visibility and limited citation impact of their research outputs. This persists notwithstanding the increasing establishment of institutional repositories and other open access initiatives within academic libraries. Although academic libraries in Nigeria have made efforts to promote open access through advocacy, repository development, and user training, these initiatives have not translated into optimal research visibility. This gap is attributed to persistent challenges such as inadequate funding, weak ICT infrastructure, absence of robust institutional policies, and low levels of awareness and utilization of open access platforms among academic staff. Furthermore, existing studies have largely focused on the availability of open access infrastructure and general adoption patterns, with limited empirical attention to the specific role of academic libraries in enhancing research visibility. Consequently, the disconnect between the availability of open access platforms and the actual visibility of Nigerian research outputs remains unresolved. This study therefore addresses this gap by examining how academic libraries contribute to promoting open access and improving research visibility in Nigerian universities.

METHODOLOGY

This study employed a descriptive survey design to examine the role of academic libraries in promoting open access and enhancing research visibility in Nigerian universities. The design was appropriate for capturing the perceptions and practices of academic staff and for analyzing relationships among variables using correlation and regression techniques. The study population comprised academic staff from two private universities in Oyo State. Lead City University (LCU) and Ajayi Crowther University (ACU) with staff populations of 715 and 505, respectively. Academic staff were selected due to their central role in knowledge

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production and engagement with open access initiatives. A proportionate stratified random sampling technique was used to ensure representation across faculties and academic ranks. Based on Krejcie and Morgan's (1970) table, a sample size of 255 was determined and proportionately allocated between the two institutions. Data were collected using a structured questionnaire covering open access promotion, utilization, strategies, and research visibility. The instrument was pilot-tested, yielding Cronbach's alpha values of 0.87 indicating high reliability. A total of 255 valid responses were obtained and screened for accuracy. Data analysis was conducted using SPSS. Descriptive statistics (mean and standard deviation) were used to summarize responses, while Pearson correlation and multiple regression analyses were employed to test relationships and determine the combined effect of the independent variables on research visibility at a 0.05 level of significance.

4.1 Descriptive Analysis of research questions

Research question 1: To what extent do academic libraries promote open access initiatives in Nigerian universities?

Table 4.1: Mean Ratings on Open Access Promotion

S/N	Item	Mean	Std. Dev.
1	Academic libraries actively promote open access initiatives	2.68	0.87
2	The library organizes awareness programs on open access	2.76	0.87
3	Librarians provide guidance on open access publishing	2.87	0.89
4	Institutional repositories are actively maintained by the library	3.04	0.77
5	The library supports self-archiving of research outputs	2.75	0.90
6	Open access policies are enforced in my institution	2.72	0.97
7	The library provides access to open access databases	2.93	0.86
8	Library staff assist researchers in depositing publications	3.04	0.82
9	Open access resources are regularly updated by the library	3.09	0.79
10	The library collaborates with faculty on open access initiatives	3.06	0.83

Table 4.1 results indicate a moderate level of agreement regarding the promotion of open access by academic libraries. While some activities such as repository maintenance (Mean = 3.04) and updating resources (Mean = 3.09) are relatively strong, others such as policy enforcement (Mean = 2.72) and self-archiving support (Mean = 2.75) are weaker. This suggests that although libraries are engaged in open access promotion, their efforts are not consistently strong across all dimensions.

Research question 2: What is the level of research visibility among academic staff in universities in Oyo State, Nigeria?

Table 4.2: Mean Ratings on Research Visibility

S/N	Item	Mean	Std. Dev.
1	My research is easily accessible online	3.21	0.75
2	My publications are indexed in search engines	3.29	0.62
3	My work receives citations from other researchers	3.07	0.72
4	Open access has increased my research visibility	3.13	0.74
5	My research reaches an international audience	3.23	0.78
6	Repository use improves discoverability of my work	2.95	0.79
7	My academic profile has improved due to open access	3.16	0.69
8	My research downloads have increased	3.27	0.65
9	Open access enhances collaboration opportunities	3.11	0.77
10	Research outputs in my university are globally visible	3.19	0.65

Table 4.2 show a generally high level of research visibility, with most mean scores above 3.00. Indicators such as indexing in search engines (Mean = 3.29) and increased downloads (Mean = 3.27) are particularly strong. However, repository-related visibility (Mean = 2.95) is slightly lower, suggesting that repositories may not be fully optimized for discoverability.

Research question 3: What is the level of awareness and utilization of open access platforms among academic staff?

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Table 4.3: Mean Ratings on Awareness and Utilization

S/N	Item	Mean	Std. Dev.
1	I am aware of open access platforms	2.89	0.73
2	I frequently use institutional repositories	2.87	0.66
3	I publish in open access journals	2.96	0.60
4	I understand how open access improves visibility	2.67	0.65
5	I deposit my research in repositories	2.96	0.65
6	I use Google Scholar and similar platforms	3.09	0.83
7	I receive support from the library for open access usage	2.83	0.75
8	I actively seek open access publishing opportunities	2.96	0.88
9	I understand copyright issues in open access publishing	2.97	0.81
10	I utilize open access for collaboration	3.07	0.79

The results on table 4.3 reveal a moderate level of awareness and utilization of open access platforms. While tools like Google Scholar (Mean = 3.09) are widely used, deeper understanding (Mean = 2.67) and institutional support (Mean = 2.83) are relatively weaker. This suggests a gap between awareness and effective utilization.

4.4 Test of Hypotheses

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between open access promotion by academic libraries and research visibility in universities in Oyo State, Nigeria.

Table 4.4: Correlation between Open Access Promotion and Research Visibility

Variables	N	r	p-value
Open Access Promotion vs Research Visibility	255	0.06	0.35

The Pearson correlation analysis in table 4.4 shows a very weak positive relationship between open access promotion and research visibility ($r = 0.06$). However, the relationship is not statistically significant ($p = 0.35 > 0.05$). This indicates that variations in open access promotion are not associated with meaningful changes in research visibility among academic staff. Since the p-value is greater than 0.05, the null hypothesis (H_{01}) is accepted.

H₀₂: There is no significant relationship between the utilization of open access platforms by academic staff and research visibility in universities in Oyo State, Nigeria.

Table 4.5: Correlation between Utilization and Research Visibility

Variables	N	r	p-value
Utilization vs Research Visibility	255	0.43	0.00

The result in table 4.5 reveals a moderate positive relationship between utilization of open access platforms and research visibility ($r = 0.43$). The relationship is statistically significant ($p = 0.00 < 0.05$), indicating that increased utilization of open access platforms is associated with a significant increase in research visibility. Since the p-value is less than 0.05, the null hypothesis (H_{02}) is rejected.

H₀₃: Open access promotion and utilization do not jointly have a significant effect on research visibility among academic staff in universities in Oyo State, Nigeria.

Table 4.6: Model Summary

R	R ²	Adjusted R ²	Std. Error of the Estimate
0.43	0.19	0.18	4.25

Table 4.6 presents the model summary of the regression analysis. The result indicates a moderate relationship between the independent variables (open access promotion and utilization) and research visibility ($R = 0.43$). The coefficient of determination ($R^2 = 0.19$) implies that approximately 19% of the variance in research visibility is explained by the predictors. The adjusted R^2

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value of 0.18 further confirms that the model has reasonable explanatory power, although a substantial proportion of variation in research visibility is influenced by other external factors not captured in the model.

Table 4.7: ANOVA

Source	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	1041.79	2	520.89	28.79	0.00
Residual	4560.07	252	18.10		
Total	5601.86	254			

Table 4.7 shows the analysis of variance (ANOVA) for the regression model. The result reveals that the model is statistically significant ($F = 28.79$, $p < 0.05$). This indicates that the independent variables, when considered together, significantly predict research visibility. Therefore, the regression model provides a good fit for the data and is appropriate for explaining variations in the dependent variable.

Table 4.8: Regression Coefficients

Predictor	B	Std. Error	Beta (β)	t	Sig.
Constant	14.91	2.66	—	5.62	0.00
Open Access Promotion	0.04	0.06	0.04	0.61	0.54
Utilization	0.53	0.07	0.43	7.52	0.00

Table 4.8 presents the regression coefficients for the predictors. The findings indicate that utilization of open access platforms has a strong positive and statistically significant effect on research visibility ($\beta = 0.43$, $t = 7.52$, $p < 0.05$). This suggests that increased use of open access platforms leads to a substantial improvement in the visibility of research outputs. In contrast, open access promotion shows a weak and non-significant effect on research visibility ($\beta = 0.04$, $t = 0.61$, $p > 0.05$), indicating that promotional activities alone do not significantly enhance research visibility. The constant value ($B = 14.91$) represents the baseline level of research visibility when all independent variables are held constant. Hence, the regression model is statistically significant ($p < 0.05$), the null hypothesis stating that open access promotion and utilization do not significantly predict research visibility is rejected. However, only utilization emerged as a significant predictor.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

This study examined the role of academic libraries in promoting open access and enhancing research visibility in Nigerian universities. The findings are discussed in relation to existing literature. The study found that open access promotion by academic libraries is moderate but not a significant predictor of research visibility. This is evident from the weak and non-significant relationship between open access promotion and research visibility ($r = 0.06$, $p > 0.05$), as well as its non-significant regression effect. This finding suggests that awareness creation and advocacy alone are insufficient to enhance research visibility, particularly when not supported by effective implementation mechanisms. This aligns with the argument of Craig et al. (2007), who observed that the open access advantage in visibility and citation is not automatic but depends on several contextual factors, including accessibility and researcher engagement. Similarly, Ezema and Okafor (2015) noted that although Nigerian academic libraries actively promote open access initiatives, such efforts are often constrained by poor infrastructure and limited compliance, thereby reducing their impact on scholarly visibility.

Another major finding of this study is that utilization of open access platforms has a strong, positive, and statistically significant influence on research visibility ($r = 0.43$, $p < 0.05$; $\beta = 0.43$, $p < 0.05$). This indicates that actual engagement with open access systems is a key determinant of research visibility. This result is consistent with prior studies. For instance, Orsu (2019) found that lecturers who actively utilized institutional repositories experienced improved dissemination and visibility of their research outputs. Likewise, Demetres and Delgado (2020), in a systematic review, reported that institutional repositories significantly enhance research accessibility, leading to increased visibility and citation impact.

Furthermore, Tennant et al. (2016) emphasized that open access improves research dissemination and global reach primarily when researchers actively deposit and share their work. This reinforces the idea that utilization, rather than mere availability, drives visibility outcomes.

The study also revealed that open access strategies have a positive and statistically significant relationship with research visibility ($r = 0.20$, $p < 0.05$), although the effect size is relatively weak. This suggests that strategic interventions such as metadata optimization, digital dissemination, and international collaboration contribute to improving visibility. This finding corroborates

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the work of Majhi, Sahu, and Behera (2023), who identified strategies such as repository indexing, digital platforms, and citation tracking as critical tools for enhancing research visibility and impact. Similarly, Wheeler et al. (2022) demonstrated that properly managed institutional repositories significantly improve discoverability and citation outcomes. However, the relatively weak strength of the relationship observed in this study suggests that strategies alone are not sufficient without active participation by researchers, reinforcing the importance of utilization.

The regression analysis showed that open access promotion and utilization jointly explain 19% of the variance in research visibility ($R^2 = 0.19$), with the model being statistically significant ($p < 0.05$). However, only utilization emerged as a significant predictor. This finding highlights a hierarchical influence of variables, where utilization is the strongest predictor and open access promotion has a negligible effect. This pattern is consistent with Lwoga and Questier (2014), who found that the adoption and usage of open access systems significantly influence research visibility and citation impact, whereas awareness alone has limited effect.

CONCLUSION

This study investigated the role of academic libraries in promoting open access and enhancing research visibility in Nigerian universities. Findings indicate that while academic libraries actively promote open access initiatives, the promotion alone does not significantly improve research visibility. Instead, the actual utilization of open access platforms by academic staff emerged as the strongest predictor of research visibility. Additionally, strategies such as repository indexing, digital dissemination and collaboration have a positive but moderate effect on research visibility. In essence, open access initiatives can only enhance research visibility when combined with active engagement, strategic implementation, and researcher participation. Academic libraries serve as facilitators, but researcher behaviour ultimately determines the effectiveness of Open access initiatives in boosting visibility and global reach.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings, the study proposes the following recommendations:

1. Academic libraries should not only promote open access but also encourage lecturers to actively deposit their work in institutional repositories and open access platforms.
2. Regular training and workshops should be organized to improve academic staff awareness, technical skills and confidence in using open access platforms.
3. Libraries should implement effective metadata, indexing and search engine optimization strategies to enhance discoverability of research outputs.
4. Institutions should formulate policies mandating the deposition of scholarly work in Open Access repositories, ensuring compliance and maximizing visibility.
5. Citation tracking and metrics systems should be adopted to measure the impact of open access initiatives on research visibility continuously.

REFERENCES

- 1) Adeyemo, O. O., & Jamogha, E. (2021). Institutional repository as a catalyst for enhanced university visibility: The case of Obafemi Awolowo University. *Covenant Journal of Library and Information Science*, 4(1). <https://journals.covenantuniversity.edu.ng/index.php/cjlis/article/view/2654>
- 2) Baro, E. E., & Eze, M. E. (2017). Perceptions and preferences of scholarly publishing in open access routes: A survey of academic librarians in Nigeria. *Information and Learning Sciences*, 118(3–4), 152–169. <https://doi.org/10.1108/ILS-03-2017-0015>
- 3) Bernal, I. (2013). Open access and the changing landscape of research impact indicators: New roles for repositories. *Publications*, 1(2), 56–71. <https://doi.org/10.3390/publications1020056>
- 4) Chukwueke, C., Nnadozie, C., & Okafor, V. (2020). Enhancing academic visibility of faculty members in Nigerian university community: The role of institutional repositories. *International Journal of Research and Scientific Innovation*, 7, 87–94. <https://rsisinternational.org/journals/ijrsi/digital-library/volume-7-issue-9/87-94.pdf>
- 5) Craig, I. D., Plume, A. M., McVeigh, M. E., & Pringle, J. (2007). Do open access articles have greater citation impact? *Journal of Informetrics*, 1(3), 239–248. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/220066010>
- 6) Demetres, M. R., & Delgado, D. (2020). The impact of institutional repositories: A systematic review. *Journal of the Medical Library Association*, 108(2), 177–184. <https://doi.org/10.5195/jmla.2020.856>

- 7) Edet, G., & Horsfall, M. (2025). Awareness and use of open access (OA) initiatives in ensuring free access to information among librarians in academic libraries in Nigeria. *International Journal of Library and Information Science Studies*, 11, 42–54.
- 8) Ezema, I. J., & Eze, J. U. (2024). Status and challenges of institutional repositories in university libraries in South-East Nigeria: Implications for visibility and ranking of Nigerian universities. *The Journal of Academic Librarianship*, 50(2). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.acalib.2023.102834>
- 9) Ezema, I. J., & Okafor, V. N. (2016). Open access institutional repositories in Nigerian academic libraries: Advocacy and issues in scholarly communication. *Library Collections, Acquisitions, & Technical Services*, 39(3–4), 45–58. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14649055.2016.1176842>
- 10) Jain, P. (2012). Promoting open access to research in academic libraries. *Library Philosophy and Practice*, 1–15. <https://www.academia.edu/download/88477388/jain.pdf>
- 11) Lwoga, E. T., & Questier, F. (2014). Faculty adoption and usage behaviour of open access scholarly communication in health science universities. *New Library World*, 115(3/4), 116–139. <https://doi.org/10.1108/NLW-01-2014-0006>
- 12) Majhi, S., Sahu, L., & Behera, K. (2023). Practices for enhancing research visibility, citations and impact: Review of literature. *Aslib Journal of Information Management*, 75(6), 1280–1305. <https://doi.org/10.1108/AJIM-11-2023-0532>
- 13) Onyebinama, C., & Chima-James, N. (2024). Promoting faculty research excellence and visibility in Nigerian universities through the open access paradigm shift. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/382338640>
- 14) Orsu, N. E. (2019). Utilization of open access repositories for visibility of academic publications by lecturers in South-East Nigeria. *International Journal of Knowledge Content Development & Technology*, 9(1), 25–39. <https://ijkcdt.journals.publicknowledgeproject.org/index.php/ijkcdt/article/view/235>
- 15) Tennant, J. P., Waldner, F., Jacques, D. C., Masuzzo, P., Collister, L. B., & Hartgerink, C. H. J. (2016). The academic, economic and societal impacts of open access: An evidence-based review. *F1000Research*, 5, 632. <https://doi.org/10.12688/f1000research.8460.3>
- 16) Wheeler, J., Pham, N. M., Arlitsch, K., & Shanks, J. D. (2022). Impact factors: Assessing the citation impact of different types of open access repositories. *Scientometrics*, 127, 4977–5003. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11192-022-04467-7>